

STRAIN ANALYSIS OF INTERFACE OF COMPOSITE FORMED BY PPR METHOD WITH COMPUTER-AIDED TECHNIQUES

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SUMMARY: The PPR method is a new method to compose metal composites. With this method, different composites such as Cu-steel, Al-steel, Sn-steel, Stainless steel-steel and etc. can be formed. In this paper, the Cu-steel and Stainless steel-steel are taken as the examples formed by the PPR method, the strains both the powder grains and the matrix on the compounding interface are studied by making use of experiment, XRD and the computer-aided techniques. The processing of experimental and analysis are introduced and the mathematics results about the strain distribution, the relationship of strain and rolling force and etc. are given. Some conclusions about the results have been made at the end of the paper.

KEYWORDS: powders plating and rolling method, strain analysis of interface, form a metallic composite, transform moire method

INTRODUCTION

PPR method is the abbreviation of Powders Plating and Rolling method. This is a new method for forming some metallic composites[1]. In this method, a kind of metal powder grains is plated on the other metal band by making use of a special technology first, then both of them are rolling together, a new composite is formed. The thickness of the composite layer formed by this technology could be 0.01mm to 0.20mm. There are some properties about this method that are different from other's of known composing technology. First, it is suitable to be industrialized broad in scope, because the metal as the composing base does not need machining; second, the producing cost is lower relatively than other composing methods; third, the technique is relative simpler than other methods; and the process of producing have almost no pollution. The products formed by this technology could be widely used in architectural decoration, preventing chemical cauterizing and transporting of electrical power and etc..

Since the metal formed the composite-layer is not a sheet but powders before rolled, it has its own special deformation laws and mechanical characteristics. These will also affect the stress and strain distribution and other mechanical properties of the metal base. there surely are many factors to affect the quality and the product cost during the process of rolling and heat treatment after-rolling, such as the state of original composition and rolled composition for the two compositing material, friction coefficients, rolling force, rolling temperature, rolling speed, the time and temperature of heat treatment and etc.. It is very important to study them

in order to bring the technique into real industrialized broad in scope. One of the important aspects is to research the mechanical performance of the composites, because this can provide very useful and essential scientific basis for the process of producing and using the composites. As these factors affect each other, it is difficult to study the mechanical performance and obtain the real magnitude and distribution of the stress and strain by theoretical method. In this paper, the Cu-steel and Stainless steel-steel are taken as the examples formed by the PPR motnod, the strains of the compounding interface are studied by combining experiment, XRD and the Transform Moire method a computer digital-image processing technique[2]. The processing of experimental and analysis are introduced and the patterns of analysis result about the strain distribution, the relationship of strain and rolling force and etc. are provided. Some conclusions about the results are made at the end of the paper.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCESS

Specimen and Experimental Materials

Because this is a metal composite, a metal band must be chosen as the matrix. In this experiment, A3 cold-rolling board is chosen as the matrix. Its size is 250 x 50 x 0.8mm. Two typical metallic powders are chosen as the material of plating layer. One is copper and another is stainless-steel. The copper grain is softer than the matrix and the stainless-steel is harder than the matrix. The diameter of the powder grains is less than 0.08mm.

Main Rolling and Measure Equipment

The rolling machine is type of SG-160 roller. The measure equipment include the type of YD-15/8 dynamic strain equipment, the type of SC 20 ray-displayer and two compress sensor that are stacked the resistance strain sheets on its surfaces, a microscope, XRD and the personal computer are also used for analyzing.

Specimen Treatment Before Rolling

The metal band is dealt with its surface by cleaning and degreases. A special technology is used to cover a kind of metallic powder on the matrix. The layer thickness of the powder grains can be controlled from 0.01mm to 0.20 mm. In order to study the deformation of matrix, the gratings of 20lines/mm had been etched on the part of combining surface by mechanical method before the powder grains were put on it.

Rolling

When both the metallic powders and the matrix are rolled together, the metallic powders on the matrix become a metal-lamella and a composite band is got. Since we want to study the relationship of rolling force and the deformation, the specimens are divided into two groups for every kind of metallic powders that covering on the matrix. Every group specimen is given different compression quantity. It is the main parameter that could be controlled by us. The rolling compressive force correspondingly is measured and recorded.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

After rolled, with a microscope the deformed grating can be observed and photographed. Then the Transform Moire method, a method of combining classical Moire experimental technique and analysis theory with computer digital-image processing technique, XRD are used to analyze the strain of the interface of the composite. The relationships of reduction and rolling force, strain and rolling force is studied.

Degree of Compression and Rolling Force

The experiment shows that the relationship between degree of compression and rolling force is very close. If the thickness of the rolled-piece before rolling is H , and the thickness after rolling is h , then the degree of compression is

$$\lambda = \frac{H-h}{H} 100\% \quad (1)$$

The experiment measured rolling forces are calculated by the formula

$$P = aS - b \quad (2)$$

Fig. 1: The relationship of P and λ

Where, S is the shift signal quantity of exported by the ray-displayer that connected with the compress sensor, a and b is material constants. In order to know them, the multiplication of minimal two is used for doing one element linear regression by the computer. Calculated λ and P , their relationships are shown in Fig. 1. Fig. 1 shows that the rolling forces are increase with the degree of compression almost linearly, and the rolling forces are different for different metal composite layers. The rolling force for the stainless steel layer is larger than the rolling force for the copper layer at the same reduction. That is because the powder grain of stainless steel is harder than the copper's. But the slopes for these two curves are closely. This means that they increase with the reduction at almost the same proportion.

The Strain Analysis on the Interface of the Matrix

Fig.2: Orthogonal grating on the interface of the composite

After being rolled, the composite lamella was peeled off, and the deformed grating was exposed. With a microscope it can be observed and photographed. The Fig.2a shows the undeformed orthogonal grating and the Fig.2b and Fig.2c show the deformed orthogonal grating. By comparing them, we found that the grating along the rolling direction did not change at all and the pitch of the grating vertically with the rolling direction increased uniformly. It means that there is no spreading in transverse direction and no strain in this direction. The deformation along the rolling direction is uniform and stretch macroscopically. The compression strain exists in microscopical location area nearly interface of the matrix. The harder the powder grain is, the more obvious the phenomenon is. This can be seen from Fig.2c that is covered by stainless steel powder grains.

Although the grating can be seen with the microscope, it will be difficult for treating them with a computer, because parts of them were damaged by the powder grains. A simulated grating was made with the computer for analysing the strain by Transformation Moire Method. The basic principle of this method is the Moir analysis theory. Since the grating consists of alternate dark and bright stripes, and the grating is vertical with x axis, then the gray levels of the digital grating deformed at any point can be represented approximately by a Fourier series as:

$$f(x) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} C_n \exp\left[j \frac{2n\pi}{p} x\right] = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} C_n \exp[j2n\pi\omega x] \quad (3)$$

Where

$$C_n = \frac{\sin(n\pi b / p)}{n\pi}, \quad \omega = \frac{1}{p} \quad (4)$$

j is imaginary unit, n is an integer and shows the time of the harmonic, p is the grating pitch, b is the width of the bright part of the grating, ω is the frequency of the first harmonic, $C_n \exp\left[j \frac{2n\pi}{p} x\right]$ is the n th harmonic component of $f(x)$. Computation of Fourier transformation of the Eqn.1 gives

$$F(\Omega) = F\{f(x)\} = \sum I_n(\Omega - n\omega) \quad (5)$$

Where $F(\Omega)$ is the frequency function of $f(x)$, then $I_n(\Omega - n\omega)$ is the n th harmonic of $f(x)$ correspondingly. The first harmonic $I_1(\Omega - \omega)$ is extracted from the spectra by Fourier band-pass filter. Both real and imaginary parts of the I_1 are shifted by ω' to the direction of the frequency centre, then $I_1(\Omega - \omega + \omega')$ is obtained. Computing the Fourier inverse transform of $I_1(\bar{\Omega} - \bar{\omega} + \bar{\omega}')$, the following is obtained

$$\begin{aligned} i_1(x) &= \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} I_1(\Omega - \omega + \omega') \exp(j2\pi\Omega x) d\Omega \\ &= C_1 \exp[j2\pi(\omega - \omega')x] \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The image of $i_1(x)$ shows a complex Moire pattern. Its real part shows a sinusoidal Moire fringes pattern that is corresponding to the equal displacement Moire pattern produced by the classical and conventional Moire method. If the grating pitch of the reference grating is $p = \frac{1}{\omega}$

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$$p = \frac{1}{\omega}$$

a: λ=26.1%

b: λ=43.5%

$$c:\lambda=65.2\%$$

Fig.3: The equal displacement Moire pattern for the Cu-steel composite interface

[3], then the grating pitch of the specimen is $p' = \frac{1}{\omega'}$. Fig.3 shows the equal displacement Moire pattern on the Cu-steel composite interface at different reductions. Obviously, the distance f of any two fringes is equal and easy to determine from the gray distribution curve of the patterns. So the average strain can be calculated by the formula

$$\varepsilon = P'/f \tag{7}$$

Table 1: The value of strain and rolling force

	copper - steel				stainless steel - steel			
Rolling force (kN)	51.66	83.96	101.50	118.16	64.93	86.52	114.18	128.95
Strain	0.25	0.57	1.06	1.48	0.25	0.53	0.92	1.21

Fig.4 shows the relationship of strain and rolling force. Because the deformation of the composite during rolling is big plastic deformation, the elastic deformation is omitted. Total strain equal plastic strain. From the curves we can know that relationship between strain and rolling force is not linear. The relationship can also be performed non-linear regression analyses by the computer and expressed by the mathematical formula

Fig.4: Relationship of strain and rolling force

$$\varepsilon = B_1 \exp(B_2 P) \quad (8)$$

Where ε is strain, P is rolling force, B_1 and B_2 are regression constants. Here $B_1 = 0.0605$, $B_2 = 0.0274$ for copper powder grains, and $B_1 = 0.0576$, $B_2 = 0.0241$ for stainless steel powder grains.

The Strain of the Composite Layer

Unlike other composite, the composite layer is a multitude of metal grains before rolling with PPR method. During the deforming process, the powder grains with bigger diameter first undergo a deformation while the powder grains with smaller diameter slide into the gaps among the grains with bigger diameter. With the pressure increasing, the powder grains gradually flatten out, close to each other, overlap each other and combine into continuous lamella. These metal grains have been cold welded into an even and continuous thin layer covering the interface of the matrix metal. Because the metal powder grains undergo a considerably big deformation in the composite processing with PPR, this affects a strong crushing function on metal grains. The result of XRD examination shows that the crystal's size inside a grain is changed with the pressure increasing. Table 2 presents the value of the crystal'

Table 2: The value of crystal's size and strain in copper grains

rolling force (kN)	0 (not rolling)	83.96	101.50	118.16
crstal's size (A)	1199	241	282	263
crystal's strain (%)	0.02	0.10	0.09	0.08

Fig. 5: SADP inside copper powder grains

size and strain examined and analyzed by XRD. The diffraction spots showed in Fig. 5 is the result of SADP. They changed into multiple spots or small arcs and took on a form of a

discontinuous ring distribution. This reveals that the crystals inside the grains are crushed and been super-fineness under the large deformation forces. It is because the crush that made the crystal' size and strain decrease in certain area.

CONCLUSIONS

(1) The rolling forces are different for different metal composite layers at the same quantity of compression with PPR method. But, the rolling force is increased with the degree of compression at almost the same proportion for defferent metal powder grains.

(2) There is no spreading in transverse direction on the interface of the matrix. This means that there is no strain and stress in this direction macroscopically.

(3) The deformation along the rolling direction is uniform on the interface of the matrix macroscopically. So the strain ϵ is also uniform. It increases with the increase of rolling force. It is a stretch strain. The strain along the transverse section and vertically the interface is not uniform, because the velocities of the two surfaces of the composite band are different and the friction forces on the two surfaces are different too. This makes the band to be bent. This problem will be studied in another paper. Since the powder grains were pressed by the rolling force, they press the matrix too. Therefore the compression strain exists in microscopical location area nearly interface of the matrix. The harder the powder grain is, the more obvious the phenomenon is.

(4) The crystal strain inside the grain is not like the strain on the interface of the matix. It does not increase with the increase of the rolling force. If the rolling force is not large enough to crush the crystals inside the grains, the strain will increase with the press force, or else the out film wrapping the metal powder grain is burst, the crystals inside the grains are crushed and the energy is released by the large deformation forces, so the strain inside the grain decreased by contrary.

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